

In Tribute and Thanks to Mike

- I am here to honor my friend and colleague Mike Rich, on the occasion of his 65th year.
- Mike: thank you for the decades of friendship, your many kindnesses and good humor.
- He introduced me to the MW bulge and he nominated me for the AAS Pierce Prize; both changed my life for the better.

Sesto 2015

Is that food or a musical instrument?

- I met Mike in the computer room at CTIO in late 1989. His interest in the MW bulge and my experience measuring the chemical composition of K giant stars fit perfectly.
- Subsequently, Mike submitted 4m telescope proposals for 1990 and 1991. We employed the Air Schmidt spectrograph (throughput 4%) to obtain the bulge spectra, much better than the long camera spectrograph at 1.5% throughput.
- Caveats: 1. it's been a while,
2. research has been a growth process

McWilliam & Rich (1994)

FIG. 7.—Plot of Fe abundance against equivalent width for Fe I lines in μ Leo. Open circles indicate all lines with measured EWs; filled circles indicate lines deemed to be unaffected by CN blending. If blended lines were used, the mean iron abundance would increase by ~ 0.3 dex, and the rms dispersion would be increased greatly.

A few things we didn't have/know:

- Temperatures
- V-band photometry
- extinction maps
- good gf values
- continuum for metal-rich stars
- many clean lines
- good alpha/Fe for Solar Neighborhood

Two figures from Fulbright, McWilliam & Rich (2007)

Inhomogeneous halo

$[\text{Al}/\text{Fe}]$ differences not a non-LTE effect

[Mn/Fe] in the bulge, MW and Sgr dSph from McWilliam, Rich & Smecker-Hane (2003)

FIG. 3.—Same as Fig. 1, but with Sgr dSph stars (*filled circles*) and Arcturus (*open diamond*) added. The error bar indicates 1σ scatter of [Mn/Fe] from Mn lines, not the error on the mean [Mn/Fe] value. We propose that the low [Mn/Fe] ratios in Sgr dSph are a consequence of enrichment of the interstellar medium by metal-poor Type Ia SNe.

sub-Ch. SNIa?

Hasselquist et al. (2017) APOGEE

red: bulge,
green: thick/halo,
black: thin disk,
blue: Sgr dSph

McWilliam et al. (2018) sub-Ch. SNIa composition for 1 star in UMi dSph

Figure 9. Estimated Ni/Fe and Mn/Fe mass ratios for the COS 171 progenitor compared to DDT and sub-Chandrasekhar-mass models. Triangles: DDT models with different deflagration to detonation transition densities (a, c, e, f) and metallicities; filled triangles indicate $Z_{\text{DDT}} = 0.010$, slightly above the effective value arising from simmering. Small filled circles connected by lines: various sub-Chandrasekhar-mass models, for different metallicities. Large filled red circle: COS 171 with the background composition of UMi 28104 subtracted. Large black cross: solar value. Note that COS 171 lies in a low-metallicity Mn/Fe region, much lower than that possible with DDT models (due to simmering increase of η); COS 171 also has low Ni/Fe, in a region sensitive to WD mass, due to the reduced role of alpha-rich freeze-out nucleosynthesis. At higher metallicity, the Ni/Fe and Mn/Fe ratios increase due to neutron-excess dependent nucleosynthesis.

Figure 10. Estimated Si/Fe and Mn/Fe mass ratios for the COS 171 progenitor compared to DDT and sub-Chandrasekhar-mass models. Symbols are the same as in Figure 9. The Si/Fe ratio increases with decreasing WD mass, likely due to a greater fraction of the core that experiences incomplete Si burning. The Si/Fe ratio indicates a WD mass near $0.94 M_{\odot}$, consistent with the value from Ni/Fe in Figure 9. Note the clean separation between WD mass and metallicity indicated by Si/Fe and Mn/Fe in this plot.

Sub-Ch. SNIa produce low [Ni/Fe] due to low T,P → reduced alpha-rich freezeout
 low [Mn/Fe] due to low neutron excess as opposed to simmering in Ch. SNIa

Kirby et al. (2019) → multiple dwarf galaxies show evidence of sub-Ch. SNIa nucleosynthesis from low [Ni/Fe] ratios.

Minelli et al. (2021): low Sc,V,Zn in LMC, Sgr, accreted GCs

Fishlock et al. (2017): low [Sc/Fe] in NS97 low-alpha stars

Figure 6. (a) [Sc/Fe] and (b) [Eu/Fe] versus [Fe/H]. The red circles indicate low- α stars, the blue open circles indicate high- α stars and the plus signs indicate TD stars. The 1σ error is shown in the bottom left of each plot.

but, normal [Si/Fe], [Ca/Fe] and [Ti/Fe]

Where are the Sc, V higher?

Prochaska & McW. (2000):
[Sc/Fe] and [V/Fe] are enhanced in the Thick Disk

Conclusion: in the dwarf galaxies, sub-Ch. SNIa dominate, but in the MW thick disk and likely the bulge, Ch. SNIa dominate Fe-group synthesis.

Q. Is this a timescale issue?

McWilliam, Fulbright, & Rich (2010)

s-process onset as a clock

Van der Swaelmen et al. (2016)
Johnson et al. (2012)

Higher SFR in bulge?

Dilution curves for Omega Cen and MW disks

100% s-process La for Omega Cen

92% s-process La, 8% r-process for MW disks

SFR difference and MW early s-process component

Van der Swaelmen et al. (2016)

The bulge shows mostly dominant r-process early composition and a steep s-process elbow near $[La/H] = -0.3$ dex.

Bensby et al. (2014) thin disk elbow near -0.45 dex

Conclusion: The bulge showed a strong S-process phase starting near $[La/H] = -0.3$ dex, While the thin disk had a lower SFR, with elbow Near $[La/H] = -0.45$ dex.

A problem to solve:

How can $[Eu/Fe]$ follow close to the MW disk trends but $[O/Fe]$ and $[Mg/Fe]$ be low by nearly 0.4 dex?

Thanks, that's all folks...